

ASILE

Global Asylum
Governance and
the European
Union's Role

The Right to Work of Asylum Seekers and Refugees

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This working paper analyses the right to work to asylum seekers and refugees. Part I briefly sets the scene, with an account of the reality of work rights restrictions for asylum seekers and refugees. Part II analysis the right to work of asylum seekers and refugees, specifically examining the right under international human rights law of global and regional scope. Concerning the former, we examine the right under international human rights law of global scope, in particular under the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights. While that instrument is often perceived as being normatively weak, due in part to a misunderstanding about the ‘progressive realization’ standard, the chapter highlights States’ immediate ‘minimum core’ obligations under the right to work. We also assess the right under African, Inter-American, and European regional human rights mechanisms, and under EU law. Some deprivations of the right to work may entail breaches of regional treaties, directly or indirectly. Restrictions on the right to work may also contribute to violations of absolute rights, such as the prohibitions on inhuman and degrading treatment, or forced labour. Part III then looks at the means of securing the right to work, namely through litigation (at domestic and regional levels) and transnational political processes.

The Right to Work of Asylum-Seekers and Refugees

Cathryn Costello* and Colm O’Cinnéide**

1. Introduction

Article 23(1) of the UDHR provides that

‘Everyone has the right to work, to free choice of employment, to just and favourable conditions of work and to protection against unemployment’.

In this paper, we characterise the right to work as a ‘composite right’ to reflect its diverse and distinct aspects, and their interactions with a range of binding international legal sources. We term this composite right, with its concerns for both the freedom, accessibility and quality of work, as the ‘right to decent work’. In this paper, references to the ‘right to work’ connote this composite right to decent work.¹ This right cuts across the traditional bifurcation between civil and political, and socio-economic rights, and is also informed by core ILO labour standards. Although many ILO instruments are concerned with the realization of the right to work, they do not enshrine it explicitly.² The first evocation of the right to work in the ILO context in 1937 related to women’s right to work.³ Before we turn to the doctrinal analysis, Section 2 briefly explores the reality of work rights restrictions for many asylum seekers and refugees.

To explore its application to asylum seekers and refugees, Section 3 analyses the right under international human rights law of global scope, in particular under the ICESCR.⁴ While that instrument is often perceived as being normatively weak, due in part to a misunderstanding about the ‘progressive realisation’ standard, we highlight States’ immediate ‘minimum core’ obligations under the right to work. We also note the

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¹ See in general the essays in Virginia Mantouvalou (ed), *The Right to Work: Legal and Philosophical Perspectives* (Hart 2015).

² ILO Employment Policy Convention No 122 (adopted 9 July 1964, entered into force 15 July 1966) 569 UNTS 65.

³ ILO, ‘Resolution concerning Women Workers’ (2–23 June 1937), cited by Angelika Nußberger, ‘International Protection of the Right to Work’, *Max Planck Encyclopedia of Public International Law* (March 2007) <<https://opil.ouplaw.com/view/10.1093/law:epil/9780199231690/law-9780199231690-e891>> accessed 11 May 2021.

⁴ Other pertinent provisions, not examined due to limitations of space, include CEDAW, art 11(1)(a); CERD, art 5(e)(i); CRC, art 32; Convention on the Protection of the Rights of All Migrant Workers and Members of Their Families (ICRMW) (adopted 18 December 1990, entered into force 1 July 2003) 2220 UNTS 3, arts 11, 25, 26, 40, 52 and 54; and Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD) (adopted 13 December 2016, entered into force 3 May 2008) 2515 UNTS 3, art 27.

important articulation of the right to work under the UN Convention of the Persons of Rights with Disabilities, which may have particular relevance relating to asylum seekers and refugees.⁵ The provisions of the CRPD transcend the dichotomy between civil and political, and economic, social and cultural rights, as is reflected in the formulation of its composite provision on work and employment, Article 27.⁶ Given that the EU was a key actor in drafting the Convention, and indeed has ratified it,⁷ this provision is of potential significance in the EU legal order, both as regards the EU's own internal standards, and a binding source in its external action.

Section 3 examines the right under African, Inter-American, and European regional human rights mechanisms. Some deprivations of the right to work may entail breaches of regional treaties, both directly (article 15 of the African Charter of Human and Peoples' Rights on the right to work) or indirectly (for example article 8 ECHR on private life or article 3 ACHR, the right to juridical personality). Restrictions on the right to work may also contribute to violations of absolute rights, such as the prohibitions on inhuman and degrading treatment, or forced labour. This is particularly the case in relation to asylum seekers and refugees, who are often in a legally vulnerable position. Indeed, in its groundbreaking ruling in *MSS v Belgium and Greece*,⁸ the ECtHR took into account the *de facto* lack of access to work as part of its assessment of Greece's violation of Article 3 ECHR. The 2017 ruling in *Chowdury and Others v Greece*⁹ is also a crucial recognition of legal vulnerability.

Section 4 then examines the right to work as a fundamental right in EU law. The right to work was one of the first fundamental rights recognised by the CJEU in its foundational era.¹⁰ The right appears in Article 15 of the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights, notably in Part II on 'Freedom', while many other work-related rights appear in the 'Equality' and 'Solidarity' chapters. The CJEU's recent caselaw affirms the right to work for asylum seekers as an aspect of human dignity.¹¹

Taking this normative backdrop into account, we examine in Section 5 two possible means of securing this right. First, we analyse domestic and EU litigation, with illustrations from three domestic systems – South Africa, Hong Kong, the UK and Ireland. South Africa is also studied as it forms one of the ASILE Case Studies.¹² The other examples are chosen because they represent a case selection based on different degrees of constitutionalisation of the human right to work, and different modes of engagement with international human rights law.

⁵ Art 27 CRPD.

⁶ Set out in full in **Appendix 1**.

⁷ Council Decision 2010/48/EC of 26 November 2009 concerning the conclusion, by the European Community, of the United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities [2010] OJ L 23/35.

⁸ *MSS v Belgium and Greece* (2011) 53 EHRR 2.

⁹ *Chowdury and Others v Greece* App No 21884/15 (ECtHR 30 March 2017); See Vladislava Stoyanova 'Sweet Taste with Bitter Roots: Forced Labour and Chowdury and Others v Greece' (2018) 1 European Human Rights Law Review 67.

¹⁰ See for example, Case 4/73 *Nold* ECLI:EU:C:1974:51 [1974] ECR 491.

¹¹ Joined Cases C-322/19 and C-385/19 *KS and MHK* ECLI:EU:C:2021:11 [2021].

¹² See generally Fatima Khan and Nandi Rayner *South Africa Country Fiche* (ASILE, October 2020).

Secondly, we examine how the right has been ‘leveraged’ transnationally in recent initiatives to encourage States hosting many refugees to grant the right to work, looking at processes focusing on Turkey, Jordan, and latterly Ethiopia. We wish to highlight in particular Jennifer Gordon’s research for the ILO on Jordan and Ethiopia, which illustrates that while they may increase access to work for *some* refugees, their overall impact on access to decent work is as yet questionable.¹³ In addition, Turkey and Jordan are included as they are ASILE case study countries.¹⁴ As Gerasimos and Verduijn note in relation to Jordan, it constitutes an apparent “good practice” example of the implementation of the Global Compact on Refugees (GCR), in that GCR activities in the country aim to complement the priorities of the Jordan Compact, particularly with regard to easing the pressures on host countries and enhancing refugee self-reliance (GCR aims 1 & 2, respectively).¹⁵ In contrast, while Turkey has taken on an active role in the GCR, none of the pledges it has made relate to the right to work for refugees, although several relate to children’s education and training.¹⁶

These country-specific processes foreshadow the emphasis in the Global Compact on Refugees (GCR) on ‘refugee self-reliance’, and so provide some early indications of the opportunities and threats in these processes.

2. Context: Work Rights Restrictions and their Impact

Before we turn to the doctrinal material, it is important to highlight the bleak situation that confronts asylum seekers and refugees. Both Mathew¹⁷ and Zetter and Raudel¹⁸ document the widespread limitations on asylum seekers’ and refugees’ right to work globally. Most refugees are in the Global South, where their access to work is often greatly limited by practices ranging from outright bans to highly restrictive permit systems. In the Global North, including in the EU, limitations on asylum seekers’ working are relatively common, often combined with restrictions on place of residence and free movement (which in themselves hinder access to work). Under Article 15 of the Recast EU Reception Conditions Directive (RCD), Member States are permitted to prohibit access to the labour

¹³ Jennifer Gordon, *Employment Working Paper No 256: Refugees and Decent Work: Lessons Learned from Recent Refugee Jobs Compacts* (2019), 2 <http://www.ilo.org/wcmsp5/groups/public/---ed_emp/---ifp_skills/documents/publication/wcms_732602.pdf> accessed 11 May 2021.

¹⁴ See generally Gerasimos Tsourapas and Simon Verduijn *Country Fiche: Jordan* (ASILE 2020); Meltem Ineli-Ciger and Ozgenur Yigit *Country Fiche: Turkey* (ASILE 2020).

¹⁵ Tsourapas and Verduijn (n 14) 16.

¹⁶ Ineli-Ciger & Yigit (n 14) 29.

¹⁷ Penelope Mathew, *Reworking the Relationship between Asylum and Employment* (Routledge 2002); Asylum Access and Global Refugee Work Rights Coalition, *Global Refugee Work Rights Report* (2014) <https://asylumaccess.org/wp-content/uploads/2014/09/FINAL_Global-Refugee-Work-Rights-Report-2014_Interactive.pdf> accessed 11 May 2021.

¹⁸ Roger Zetter and Héloïse Raudel, *Refugees' Right to Work and Access to Labor Market. An Assessment (Part 1)* (2016) <<https://www.knomad.org/publication/refugees-right-work-and-access-labor-markets-assessment-part-1>> accessed 11 May 2021.

market for up to 9 months.¹⁹ The practice of EU states varies significantly in their implementation of the RCD, in some instances treating different categories of asylum seekers differently.²⁰

Moreover, there are many ways that asylum processes may undermine the right to work. If asylum procedures are protracted, periods spent in limbo render applicants less employable later.²¹ Furthermore, if processes fail to recognize refugees or siphon them into insecure statuses, the formal right of access to work enjoyed by recognized refugees is rendered illusory. Periods awaiting status determination have been demonstrated to have a significant later impact on work prospects. While recognised refugees generally have the right to work in the Global North, many asylum processes have indeterminate outcomes, and some are granted informal domestic ‘humanitarian’ statuses, generally of short duration. Such short precarious statuses may not entail a formal right to work. Or even if they do, practical access to work is often difficult or impossible, as such statuses make workers unattractive to employers.

Globally, welfare payments and/or humanitarian assistance are often assumed to compensate for this lack of legal access to work. However, these funds, even if they are available, rarely provide an adequate standard of living, so asylum seekers and refugees must find some way to earn their living—usually in the ‘informal sector’. The relationship between work and welfare is complex, and varies from state to state. In some instance, where states offer a formal right to work (even if it is ineffective) they accordingly seek to reduce welfare entitlements, in a manner which may undermine the right to a decent standard of living. For instance, in some EU Member States where the waiting time for access to employment has been reduced (albeit subject to stringent sector restrictions), the authorities have relied on this fact to treat asylum seekers as ‘wilfully unemployed’ and deny welfare benefits.²² While the complex interplay between work and welfare rights is outside the scope of this paper, the dynamic is salient to human rights law if measures in fact leave asylum seekers or refugees in inhuman and degrading living conditions.

As mentioned, in the absence of decent levels of social support, most refugees and asylum seekers work in the informal sector. This term encompasses diverse forms of work, and in many States, the informal sector accounts for most work.²³ The informal sector is generally underregulated and exploitative, reflecting gendered and racialized hierarchies (as does formal work). Yet, the ‘informal sector’ may also include self-employment and

¹⁹ Directive 2013/33/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 26 June 2013 laying down standards for the reception of applicants for international protection [2013] OJ L 180/96 (Reception Conditions Directive).

²⁰ See generally European Migration Network (EMN), *Ad Hoc Query on the right to work for asylum seekers* (2019) <https://ec.europa.eu/home-affairs/sites/default/files/20195_uk_right_to_work_for_asylum_seekers.pdf> accessed 11 May 2021.

²¹ Moritz Marbach, and Jens Hainmueller, and Dominik Hangartner, ‘The Long-Term Impact of Employment Bans on the Economic Integration of Refugees’ (2018) 4(9) *Science Advances*.

²² AIDA, *Country Report: Cyprus* (2019) <https://asylumineurope.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/04/report-download_aida_cy_2019update.pdf> accessed 11 May 2021.

²³ ILO, *Women and Men in the Informal Economy: A Statistical Picture* (3rd edn, 2018) <https://www.ilo.org/global/publications/books/WCMS_626831/lang--en/index.htm> accessed 11 May 2021.

commercial activities that offer better conditions than 'formal' employment, in particular if 'formality' connotes working under highly restrictive migration statuses.²⁴ These generally entail increased dependency on employers, in-built risks of exploitation and even forced labour.²⁵ Gaining a deeper understanding of 'informal' work is an urgent task for those who seek to advocate and work for better refugee work rights.²⁶

A final issue relating to scope: This paper focuses on the rights of adults at liberty. Child labour is often prevalent amongst refugee communities when other economic opportunities are foreclosed, and raises distinctive human rights issues in need of further scholarly attention.²⁷

3. The Right to Work in International Human Rights Law

(a) The Dual Value of the Right to Work

The right to work has both instrumental and intrinsic value. Its instrumental value lies in the fact that work enables individuals to participate in social, economic, and political life, and crucially to earn a livelihood. Work is also intrinsically valuable, as people derive dignity and self-worth from their engagement with their environments and others through work. Both aspects are widely recognized. The UN Committee on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (CESCR)'s General Comment 18 acknowledges that work is both 'essential for realizing other human rights' and 'an inseparable and inherent part of human dignity'.²⁸

The 'dual value' of this right is practically important, in particular for asylum seekers and refugees subject to prohibitions on working. States sometimes attempt to argue that providing financial support justifies work restrictions. However, while such financial assistance may provide a livelihood, it does not address the denial of the dignity-enhancing role of work. This is a key aspect of the right, so as is discussed further below, even if the right to an adequate livelihood (article 11 ICESCR) is guaranteed, States are obliged to respect the intrinsic value of access to dignified work.

²⁴ On the links between migration status and labour exploitation, see generally Cathryn Costello and Mark Freedland, *Migrants at Work: Immigration and Vulnerability in Labour Law* (OUP 2015).

²⁵ Cathryn Costello, 'Migrants and Forced Labour: A Labour Law Response' in Alan Boggand others (eds), *The Autonomy of Labour Law* (Hart 2014) 189.

²⁶ See generally Diamond Ashiagbor (ed), *Re-Imagining Labour Law for Development: Informal Work in the Global North and South* (Hart 2019).

²⁷ Manfred Liebel, 'Economic and Labor Rights of Children' in Jonathan Todres and Shani M King (eds), *The Oxford Handbook of Children's Rights Law* (OUP 2020).

²⁸ CESCR, 'General Comment No 18: The Right to Work, Article 6 of ICESCR' (6 February 2006) UN Doc E/C.12/GC/18.

(b) The Substantive Scope of the Right to Work in ICESCR

The affirmation of the right to decent work in article 23(1) UDHR finds binding expression in several international human rights treaties, most notably articles 6 and 7 ICESCR. Article 6 provides that individuals should enjoy free choice of labour ('work which he freely chooses or accepts'), and obliges States Parties to take 'appropriate steps to safeguard this right', in order to achieve 'steady economic, social and cultural development and full and productive employment' under 'conditions safeguarding fundamental political and economic freedoms'. Article 7 ICESCR specifies the right to 'just and favourable conditions of work'. In interpreting article 6, the CESCR has emphasized that while it does not create a right to obtain employment as such, it 'affirms the obligation of States Parties to assure individuals their right to freely chosen or accepted work', encompassing the right 'not to be deprived of work unfairly' or to be 'forced in any way whatsoever to exercise or engage in employment'.²⁹ Furthermore, '[w]ork as ... must be decent work', which 'provides an income allowing workers to support themselves and their families' and must be compatible with the 'physical and mental integrity' of the worker.³⁰

The Committee interprets ICESCR as requiring States to secure the 'following interdependent and essential elements' of the right to work,³¹ namely (i) *availability*, in the sense that States Parties must establish specialized services to assist and support individuals in finding employment;³² (ii) *accessibility*, in the sense that States must prohibit discrimination in access to employment, and also implement national policies to promote equal access to the labour market,³³ and (iii) *acceptability*, in the sense that States must take steps to protect the rights of workers to enjoy just and favourable conditions of work, and to protect vulnerable categories of workers against exploitation—including by reducing 'to the fullest extent possible the number of workers outside the formal economy'.³⁴

These obligations are often wrongly written off as soft. However, article 2(1) ICESCR obliges States to give effect to their obligations under the Covenant 'individually and through international assistance and cooperation (...) to the maximum of [their] available resources, with a view to achieving progressively the full realization of the rights recognized in the present Covenant by all appropriate means'. Article 2(2) builds on this general requirement by requiring States Parties to guarantee the Covenant rights 'without discrimination', while article 4 provides that any limitations on the enjoyment of these rights must be 'compatible with the nature of these rights and solely for the purpose of promoting the general welfare in a democratic society'. The reference to 'progressive realisation' is often wrongly taken to dilute the ICESCR duties generally, but legally, some obligations thereunder are of immediate effect, and subject to non-regression.³⁵

²⁹ *ibid* para 4.

³⁰ *ibid* para 7.

³¹ *ibid* para 12.

³² *ibid* para 19.

³³ *ibid* para 12.

³⁴ *ibid* para 10.

³⁵ See generally CESCR, 'General Comment No 3: The Nature of States Parties' Obligations' (14 December 1990) UN Doc E/1991/23; Magdalena Sepúlveda Carmona, *The Nature of the Obligations under the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights* (Intersentia 2003); Economic and Social Council, 'The Limburg Principles on the Implementation of the

Obligations of immediate effect relate to the 'minimum core' of the rights, which in relation to the right to work include (i) ensuring non-discriminatory access to employment, (ii) taking measures to avoid labour exploitation, and (iii) adopting national employment strategies targeting 'disadvantaged and marginalized individuals and groups'.³⁶ This set of minimum core entitlements recognizes the intrinsic value of work, and is the minimum level of action that States are obliged to undertake under the Covenant.³⁷

(c) The Personal and Geographic Scope of the Right to Work in ICESCR

Article 6 ICESCR applies to 'everyone'. Its universal personal scope is buttressed by the non-discrimination guarantee in article 2(2), part of the 'minimum core'. Accordingly, as the CESCR has noted, article 6 and other ICESCR rights apply 'to everyone including non-nationals, such as refugees, asylum seekers, stateless persons, migrant workers and victims of international trafficking, regardless of legal status and documentation'.³⁸ In its General Comment 23, the CESCR affirmed that article 7 ICESCR is a 'right of everyone, without distinction of any kind', specifically mentioning 'workers in the informal sector, migrant workers, workers from ethnic and other minorities, ...refugee workers'.³⁹ The Committee further explicitly acknowledged the vulnerability of refugees due to their 'often precarious legal status', accordingly stating that States should 'enact legislation enabling refugees to work and under conditions no less favourable than for nationals'.⁴⁰ Notably, this 'national treatment' standard is higher than the requirement under the Refugee Convention. This reasoning applies equally to article 6 ICESCR.

However, there is a complicating factor. While article 2(2) enshrines non-discrimination, article 2(3) provides that '[d]eveloping countries, with due regard to human rights and their national economy, may determine to what extent they would guarantee the economic rights recognized in the present Covenant to non-nationals'. The term 'developing countries' here is not defined, however, its usage within the UN offers clarity.⁴¹ Article 2(3) thus appears at first glance to permit the States that host most refugees to deny their economic rights. However, we do not share the view that the

International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights' (8 January 1987) UN Doc E/CN.4/1987/17, annex (Limburg Principles).

³⁶ CESCR, 'General Comment No 18' (n 28) para 31.

³⁷ See Colm O'Cinnéide, 'The Right to Work in International Human Rights Law' in Virginia Mantouvalou (ed), *The Right to Work: Legal and Philosophical Perspectives* (Hart 2015).

³⁸ CESCR, 'General Comment No 20, Non-Discrimination in Economic, Social and Cultural Rights' (2 July 2009) UN Doc E/C.12/GC/20 para 30.

³⁹ CESCR, 'General Comment No 23 (2016) on the Right to Just and Favourable Conditions of Work (Article 7 of the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights)' (27 April 2016) UN Doc E/C.12/GC/23 para 5.

⁴⁰ *Ibid*, para 47 (e).

⁴¹ Ben Saul, David Kinley, and Jaqueline Mowbray, *The International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights: Commentary, Cases and Materials* (OUP 2014) 214–17.

provision is really ‘potentially fatal ... for the overwhelming majority of refugees’,⁴² when interpreted correctly. As a general matter, article 2(3) is a potential exception to the general prohibition on non-discrimination in article 2(2), and should be interpreted narrowly.⁴³

To rely on article 2(3), States must have ‘due regard to human rights’, and so may not rely on article 2(3) to breach any non-economic rights under the Covenant, or indeed other human rights treaties. While the ‘right to work’ is clearly an ‘economic right’,⁴⁴ article 2(3) does not provide a basis for any work rights restrictions that may also entail breaches of, say, the right to be free from slavery or forced labour, or other non-economic rights.⁴⁵ Article 2(3) cannot be used to limit rights under other human rights treaties, including the right to work under regional treaties.⁴⁶ Secondly, the provision requires ‘due regard’ to the ‘national economy’. To establish a rational degree of connection between a work rights restriction and the ‘national economy’, States would need to demonstrate that excluding non-nationals is economically beneficial. However, labour market exclusions generally are not. They risk creating a shadow workforce in the informal sector, ripe for exploitation, undercutting local workers’ rights in affected sector. Far from bringing benefits to the national economy, work rights restrictions are counterproductive.⁴⁷ Notably, it appears that no State has explicitly invoked the provisions of article 2(3) to justify discrimination against non-nationals.⁴⁸ Finally, in light of the ambiguities of the text, we may also have regard to the *travaux préparatoires*,⁴⁹ which reveal that article 2(3) was inserted to ensure that formerly colonized States could take action to prevent non-nationals playing a dominant role in their economic life.⁵⁰ In other words, article 2(3) was intended to permit newly independent States to limit the role of a formerly dominant colonial elite, rather than to target a vulnerable population.

Our conclusion on the general applicability of article 6 ICESCR to refugees and asylum seekers on a non-discriminatory basis means that bans and other significant restrictions on asylum seekers and refugees working are arguably in breach, unless they can be shown to be objectively justified under article 4.⁵¹ While article 4 permits some limitations on rights, they must be ‘compatible with the nature of these rights and solely for the

⁴² James C Hathaway, ‘The Architecture of the UN Refugee Convention and Protocol’ in Cathryn Costello, Michelle Foster and Jane McAdam (eds), *The Oxford Handbook of International Refugee Law* (OUP 2021 *forthcoming*).

⁴³ Limburg Principles (n 35) para 43.

⁴⁴ See Saul, Kinley, and Mowbray (n 41) 217.

⁴⁵ See section 3(c)(ii) for ECHR discussion.

⁴⁶ Sepúlveda Carmona (n 35) 415, noting that States may not rely on article 2(3) to limit the right to work under article 15 of the African Charter of Human and Peoples’ Rights.

⁴⁷ See generally Michael Clemens, Cindy Huang, and Jimmy Graham, ‘The Economic and Fiscal Effects of Granting Refugees Formal Labor Market Access’ (2018) <<https://www.cgdev.org/sites/default/files/economic-and-fiscal-effects-granting-refugees-formal-labor-market-access-brief.pdf>> accessed 11 May 2021.

⁴⁸ Saul, Kinley, and Mowbray (n 41) 217.

⁴⁹ Vienna Convention on the Law of Treaties (adopted 22 May 1969, entered into force 27 January 1980) 1155 UNTS 331, art 32.

⁵⁰ Saul, Kinley, and Mowbray (n 41); See also EVO Dankwa, ‘Working Paper on Article 2(3) of the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights’ (1987) 9(2) Human Rights Quarterly 230.

⁵¹ CESCR, ‘General Comment No 18’ (n 28) para 31.

purpose of promoting the general welfare in a democratic society'.⁵² Given that non-discriminatory access to work is part of the 'minimum core' of the right to work, and so essential to human dignity, States should have to show compelling justification for denying asylum seekers and refugees access to employment. Similarly, State failures to protect refugees and asylum seekers against labour exploitation will also *prima facie* breach the 'minimum core' requirements of article 6, as will their exclusion from national employment plans: again, any limitation of these core rights should have to be supported by compelling justification.

It is noteworthy that only two States Parties to the ICESCR have entered reservations relating to the scope of article 6 ICESCR, France and UK.⁵³ However, such reservations must be interpreted narrowly, and subject to the overall object and purpose of ICESCR to protect human dignity.⁵⁴ As such, the UK reservation is dubious, as restrictions on their access to work will have little or no tangible impact on the 'employment opportunities' of workers in general.

The CESCR gives effect to these obligations in its monitoring via States' periodic reports, and of late individual complaints.⁵⁵ The Committee increasingly expresses concern about high unemployment among refugees, calling on States to take concrete and specific measures.⁵⁶ It also calls on States to remove work bans on asylum seekers, to expedite asylum processing, and take measures to eliminate discrimination in work against refugees and asylum seekers.⁵⁷ This jurisprudence remains a work in progress. Uncertainty persists as to the exact scope of State obligations to those with irregular migration status, and where, for instance, unregistered asylum seekers and unrecognized refugees fall in that discussion.⁵⁸

⁵² See generally Amrei Müller, 'Limitations to and Derogations from Economic, Social and Cultural Rights' (2009) 9(4) Human Rights Law Review 557.

⁵³ France declared that article 6 should not be interpreted as 'derogating from provisions governing the access of aliens to employment', while the UK reserved 'the right to interpret article 6 as not precluding the imposition of restrictions, based on place of birth or residence qualifications, on the taking of employment in any particular region or territory for the purpose of safeguarding the employment opportunities of workers in that region or territory'.

⁵⁴ Ineta Ziemele and Lasma Liede, 'Reservations to Human Rights Treaties' (2013) 24(4) European Journal of International Law 1135.

⁵⁵ UNGA, 'Optional Protocol to the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights' (adopted 10 December 2008, entered into force 5 May 2013) UN Doc A/RES/63/117.

⁵⁶ See eg CESCR, 'Concluding Observations: Azerbaijan' (14 December 2004) UN Doc E/C.12/1/Add.104 para 17; CESCR, 'Concluding Observations: Denmark' (14 December 2004) UN Doc E/C.12/1/Add.102 paras 15, 26.

⁵⁷ See eg CESCR, 'Concluding Observations: Slovakia' (14 November 2019) UN Doc E/C.12/SVK/CO/3 paras 20–21; CESCR, 'Concluding Observations: Israel' (12 November 2019) UN doc E/C.12/ISR/CO/4 paras 22–23; CESCR, 'Concluding Observations: Belgium' (26 March 2020) UN Doc E/C.12/BEL/CO/5 paras 22–23.

⁵⁸ See generally Colm O'Cinnéide, 'The Human Rights of Migrants with Irregular Status: Giving Substance to Aspirations of Universalism' in Sarah Spencer and Anna Triandafyllidou (eds), *Migrants with Irregular Status in Europe: Evolving Conceptual and Policy Challenges* (Springer 2020).

(d) ICESCR and international cooperation

Article 28 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights provides that ‘everyone is entitled to a social and *international* order in which the rights and freedoms set forth in this Declaration can be fully realized.’ ICESCR contains a binding provision reflecting this cooperative obligation, when in Article 2 (1) it refers the obligation, ‘to take steps, individually *and through international assistance and co-operation*, especially economic and technical, to the maximum of its available resources, with a view to achieving progressively the full realization of the rights recognized in the present Covenant by all appropriate means.’ (emphasis added). Articles 22 and 23 further emphasise the important role of various forms of international action and cooperation for the achievement of ICESCR rights, with Article 23 setting out examples of the type of measures that may constitute ‘international action for the achievement of the rights recognized in the present Covenant’.⁵⁹

The CESCR has emphasized that state parties should recognize the essential role of international cooperation and comply with the commitment to take joint and separate action to achieve the full realization of the right to work.⁶⁰ Concerning the right to just and favourable conditions of work under Article 7, the Committee has affirmed that states are required to take steps both individually and through international assistance and cooperation, especially economic and technical (including the assistance of specialized United Nations agencies) to achieve the full realization of the right to just and favourable conditions of work.⁶¹ It has also affirmed that states parties are to respond to requests for international assistance by providing ‘economic and technical assistance and technology transfer and by promoting transnational dialogue between employer and worker organisations among other measures (...) in a manner consistent with human rights standards.’⁶² This includes the obligation to respect the right to just and favourable conditions of work in the conclusion and implementation of international agreements, including in bilateral, regional and multilateral trade and investment agreements.⁶³

(e) The Right to Work under the Refugee Convention

The Refugee Convention contains detailed provisions on work, reflecting its aim to create a legal status for millions of refugees left in limbo Europe at the time of its drafting. Its rights catalogue is wide, including the right of association and to form trade unions (article 15), access to wage-earning employment (article 17), liberal professions (article 19), public relief (article 23), protection of labour legislation and social security (article 24), and the issuance of travel documents (article 28). Famously, Henkin, as US representative in the drafting process, stated that ‘without the right to work all other rights were meaningless. Without that right no refugee could even become assimilated within his

⁵⁹ F. Coomans, “Some Remarks on the Extraterritorial Application of the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights”, F. Coomans & M. Kamminga (eds) *Extraterritorial Application of Human Rights Treaties* (2004) 183(emphasis added).

⁶⁰ CESCR, ‘General Comment No 18’ (n 28) para. 29.

⁶¹ CESCR, ‘General Comment No. 23’ (n 39), para. 66.

⁶² *Ibid.*

⁶³ *Ibid.*

country of residence'.⁶⁴ This section is brief, as these provisions are examined thoroughly elsewhere.⁶⁵ We share Edwards' conclusion that 'the right to work under Article 6 ICESCR is arguably wider in scope than the [Refugee] Convention'.⁶⁶ Crucially, under article 5 of the Refugee Convention, refugees will usually be entitled benefit of the higher standards under ICESCR.

Notwithstanding their centrality, the work-related rights reflect the compromises of the drafting process, in particular the assumption that an immediate work right for refugees was not feasible given the post-war devastation of European economies. Article 17 on 'wage-earning employment' is applicable to 'lawfully staying' refugees, with the standard of treatment set as 'the most favourable treatment accorded to nationals of a foreign country in the same circumstances'.⁶⁷ In contrast, article 18 on 'self-employment' is applicable to the wider category of refugees, those 'lawfully in' the territory, but at a lower standard of protection, namely that applicable to 'aliens generally in the same circumstances', as is article 19 on 'liberal professions'.

'Lawfully staying' in article 17 on employment connotes a stronger 'degree of attachment' than 'lawfully in' in article 18 on self-employment, to borrow Hathaway's phrase.⁶⁸ In the French text, 'lawfully staying' is 'résident régulièment'. Once a refugee is recognized (including on a *prima facie* basis) undoubtedly, she should thereby be treated as 'lawfully staying'. Crucially, 'lawfully staying' should also include asylum seekers, if their claims are not dealt with within a reasonable time.⁶⁹ 'Lawfully in', the standard for self-employment, is a weaker degree of attachment, including those admitted for any period, including asylum seekers, and those remaining under temporary or other informal protections.⁷⁰

The right to work is to be accorded at the 'most favourable foreigner' standard.⁷¹ To illustrate, this should mean that refugees are granted the same work rights as EU citizens (in EU Member States) or nationals of any such States who enjoy special rights under bilateral or regional agreements. Otherwise, if there is no such 'privileged' foreigner, the Michigan Guidelines urge that the appropriate comparator be permanent residents.⁷² Notably, Edwards notes that most of the many reservations to the right to work under the Convention purport to exclude refugees the standard that ought to be applicable as 'most favourable' (i.e. that under regional and other preferential agreements) or clarify that

⁶⁴ UN Ad Hoc Committee on Refugees and Stateless Persons, 'Summary Record of the Thirty-Seventh Meeting' (16 August 1950), UN doc E/AC.32.SR.37, 12 (Mr Henkin, US).

⁶⁵ James Hathaway, *The Rights of Refugees under International Law* (CUP 2005) 730–86; Mathew (n 17); Alice Edwards, 'Part 4 Gainful Employment' in Andreas Zimmermann, Jonas Dörschner, and Felix Machts (eds), *The 1951 Convention relating to the Status of Refugees and Its 1967 Protocol: A Commentary* (OUP 2011); University of Michigan Law School, 'The Michigan Guidelines on the Right to Work' (2010). <<https://www.refworld.org/docid/4bbaf1242.html>> accessed 11 May 2021 (Michigan Guidelines).

⁶⁶ Alice Edwards, 'Human Rights, Refugees, and The Right "To Enjoy" Asylum' (2005) 17 *International Journal of Refugee Law* 293.

⁶⁷ The drafting history reveals that a stronger version was contemplated and rejected. Mathew (n 17) 86.

⁶⁸ See further Hathaway, *Rights* (n 65) ch 3.

⁶⁹ See Michigan Guidelines (n 65) para 8.

⁷⁰ See further Hathaway, *Rights* (n 65) 173–86.

⁷¹ Refugee Convention, art 6.

⁷² Michigan Guidelines (n 65) para 11.

article 17 does not preclude requiring refugees to get work permits.⁷³ For self-employment, the 'aliens generally' standard for the right to self-employment requires the State to treat refugees as it does other foreigners in general, which may offer little economic freedom in practice.

Overall, the Refugee Convention's work provisions are important, but limited. However, as already noted, by virtue of article 5 of the Refugee Convention, refugees are entitled to the benefit of higher human rights standards, which generally will be those under ICESCR, or in particular in Africa, under its regional human rights instrument.

(f) Collective aspects of the right to work – trades unions

ICESCR protects the right of to form and join a trade union or other association, including employer organizations or associations of professionals, for the promotion and protection of their economic and social interests.⁷⁴ Non-nationals, including refugees, are equally allowed to form or join a trade union, employer organization or association of liberal professionals, subject to the rules of organization itself, unless it can be lawfully restricted by the State. Further, any differential treatment between nationals and non-nationals to form or join any labour related organizations must be reasonable and objective so as not to amount to discrimination.⁷⁵ Article 15 CSR51 accords refugees 'most favourable alien' treatment to form or join trade unions and associations that are non-political and non-profit-making. This includes employer or professional associations. The ILO recommends that states should adopt national policies that 'facilitate the participation of all workers, including refugees and other forcibly displaced persons, in representative organizations, including in relation to their right to form and join trade unions, participate in collective bargaining mechanisms and to access justice and judicial remedies against abusive working conditions.'⁷⁶

(g) The UNCRPD

Article 27 of the UNCRPD is set out in full in Appendix 1. It engages with the right to work as set out in ICESCR, but like the other provisions of this ground-breaking Convention, applies a disability lens, and integrates negative and positive duties. Its obligations include a duty to ensure the participation of persons with disabilities in the labour market, including through reasonable accommodation. A detailed analysis of this provision is outside the scope of this paper, but the provision's importance for EU asylum policy (both internal and external) is evident.

⁷³ Edwards, 'Part 4 Gainful Employment'(n 65) 957.

⁷⁴ ICESCR Article 8. It also recognises the right for trade unions to established national (con)federations, to join international trade union organizations and to function freely. It also establishes a right to strike. The right to form and join trade unions and other associations is also recognized in Article 22 ICCPR. See also: ILO, 'Freedom of Association and Protection of the Right to Organise Convention (No.087)' (1948), Art. 2.

⁷⁵ ICESCR, note 6 above, Article 2(3).

⁷⁶ ILO Guiding Principles, Principle 23(b).

4. The Right to Work in Regional Human Rights Law

(a) The African Charter of Human and Peoples' Rights

The African Charter adopts an integrated approach to human rights, both civil and political and socio-economic.⁷⁷ Article 15 recognizes that '[e]very individual shall have the right to work under equitable and satisfactory conditions'. The Commission's initial interpretation of the right to work has emphasized how it guarantees equal access to decent work for all, generating obligations on States to regulate the conduct of private employers as well as State organs. Its approach reflects the 'minimum core' requirements of article 6 ICESCR.⁷⁸

There is nothing in the Charter to indicate that refugees and asylum seekers are excluded from its protection. Indeed, the African Commission on Human and Peoples' Rights (ACHRP) has repeatedly affirmed the equal application of the Charter to national and non-nationals alike. While its jurisprudence has not focused on refugees and asylum seekers in detail,⁷⁹ in the case of *Rencontre Africaine pour la Défense des Droits de l'Homme v Zambia* it confirmed that States must secure the rights under the Charter to everyone within their jurisdiction, including non-nationals.⁸⁰ In a number of resolutions and comments on State reports, the Commission has also called for speedier processing of asylum applications,⁸¹ as well as the integration of refugees into the host society.⁸²

(b) The Inter-American System

The Charter of the Organisation of American States (OAS) recognizes the importance of the right to work. Article 45(b) of the 1948 OAS Charter states:

Work is a right and a social duty, it gives dignity to the one who performs it, and it should be performed under conditions, including a system of fair wages, that ensure life, health, and a decent standard of living for the worker and his family,

⁷⁷ Manisuli Ssenyonjo, 'Analysing the Economic and Cultural Rights Jurisprudence of the African Commission' (2011) 29(3) *Netherlands Quarterly of Human Rights* 358.

⁷⁸ Rachel Murray, *The African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights: A Commentary* (OUP 2019) 389–97.

⁷⁹ See further Gina Bekker, 'The Protection of Asylum Seekers and Refugees within the African Regional Human Rights System' (2013) 13 *African Human Rights Law Journal* 1.

⁸⁰ *Rencontre Africaine pour la Défense des Droits de l'Homme v Zambia* (2000) AHRLR 321 (ACHPR 1996); see also *African Institute for Human Rights and Development (on behalf of Sierra Leonean refugees in Guinea) v Guinea* (2004) AHRLR 57 (ACHPR 2004).

⁸¹ See ACHRP, 'Concluding Observations and Recommendations on the 1st Periodic Report of the Union of South Africa' (21 November–5 December 2005) para 26.

⁸² ACHRP, 'Concluding Observations and Recommendations on the 3rd Periodic Report of the Republic of Sudan' (13–27 May 2009) para 39.

both during his working years and in his old age, or when any circumstance deprives him of the possibility of working.⁸³

The legally binding American Convention on Human Rights (ACHR), later drafted under the auspices of the OAS, mainly covers on civil and political rights. However, article 26 of the ACHR commits States Parties to progressively realizing the socio-economic rights recognized in the OAS Charter, including the right to work. Furthermore, the San Salvador Protocol to the Convention, which protects various socio-economic rights, provides in article 6(1) that: '[e]veryone has the right to work, which includes the opportunity to seek the means for living a dignified and decent existence by performing a freely elected or accepted lawful activity'. Not every State party to the ACHR has ratified this Protocol.⁸⁴

Crucially, the Inter-American Commission and Court of Human Rights recognize the interconnectedness of civil and political and socio-economic rights. When they interpret and apply the Inter-American rights, they take into account the dual value of the right to work.⁸⁵ In particular, the Commission and Court have affirmed aspects of the right to work of undocumented migrants under the right to equality and the right to juridical personality. For example, in its *Advisory Opinion on the Juridical Condition and Rights of Undocumented Migrants*,⁸⁶ the Court concluded that denying undocumented migrants protection against workplace exploitation would be discriminatory. In *Undocumented Workers v United States of America*,⁸⁷ the Commission deemed legal protection against workplace exploitation to be a 'civil right' enjoyed under the right to juridical personality, and held that a failure to provide proper remedies for such exploitation constituted unjustified discrimination contrary to the requirements of the OAS Charter. The reasoning would seem to apply to asylum seekers and refugees *a fortiori*.

(c) The Council of Europe System

The Council of Europe system reflects the bifurcation between civil and political and socio-economic rights. The explicit right to work is enshrined within the weaker socio-economic instrument, the European Social Charter. However, it also enjoys a degree of indirect protection via the ECHR.

i. European Social Charter

⁸³ See also 'American Declaration of the Rights and Duties of Man' adopted by the Ninth International Conference of American States (1948) reprinted in Basic Documents Pertaining to Human Rights in the Inter-American System OEA/Ser L V/II.82 Doc 6 Rev 1, 17(1992) art XIV.

⁸⁴ The Protocol has been ratified by sixteen OAS States.

⁸⁵ See in general Verónica Gómez, 'Economic, Social, and Cultural Rights in the Inter-American System' in Mashood Baderin and Robert McCorquodale (eds), *Economic, Social, and Cultural Rights in Action* (OUP 2007).

⁸⁶ *Juridical Condition and Rights of the Undocumented Migrants*, Advisory Opinion OC-18, Inter-American Court of Human Rights Series A No 18 (17 September 2003).

⁸⁷ *Undocumented Workers v United States of America*, Inter-American Commission on Human Rights Report No 50/16, Case No 12.834 (30 June 2016).

Adopted in 1961, the ESC predates ICESCR by five years, the first international human rights treaty on socio-economic rights, intended to complement the ECHR. The right to work is central to the ESC,⁸⁸ appearing in article 1, which requires States (i) to take positive steps to maintain high levels of employment through the implementation of adequately resourced national employment and job creation policies, and (ii) to protect individuals against discrimination, forced labour and other forms of exploitation. The decency of work is protected under a number of other inter-connected ESC rights, including in particular the detailed provisions of article 2 (the right to just conditions of work), article 3 (the right to healthy and safe working conditions), and article 4 (the right to fair remuneration).

The European Committee on Social Rights (ECSR) interprets article 1 and these other provisions systematically.⁸⁹ They are read as imposing a range of detailed positive obligations on States to ensure workers enjoy access to decent work, with the Committee monitoring compliance with these requirements through a State reporting process and also a 'collective complaints' mechanism.

Unlike most other human rights treaties, the ESC does not generally apply to nationals and non-national alike. The Appendix to the ESC governing the scope of the Charter limits it to non-nationals of *State Parties*.⁹⁰ However, the exclusion is qualified by a provision covering 'refugees as defined in the [Refugee Convention]'. For those who are 'lawfully staying in its territory', States are required to extend 'treatment as favourable as possible, and in any case not less favourable than under the obligations accepted by the Party under the said convention and under any other existing international instruments applicable to those refugees'. The ECSR interprets this provision as requiring equal treatment between refugees and asylum seekers and nationals, except where a State party can show a compelling justification for differential treatment, and crucially that refugees should in all circumstances enjoy the protection of the essential features of the relevant ESC rights.⁹¹ This focus on the 'core' of ESC rights, which would appear to cover the central elements of the right to decent work as protected by articles 1–4 ESC, has again echoes of the core requirements of article 6 ICESCR.

The ESC's provisions in respect of the right to work are particularly important from the perspective of EU law.⁹² Article 151 TFEU recognises that the ESC sets out 'fundamental social rights' which also constitute core objectives of EU social policy, which include the 'promotion of employment, improved living and working conditions'. The Preamble of the EU Charter makes specific reference to the ESC, stating that its purpose is to affirm the rights set out *inter alia* 'the Social Charters adopted by the Union and by the Council of Europe'. Furthermore, many of the rights and principles set out in the EU Charter overlap

⁸⁸ Simon Deakin, 'The Right to Work' in Niklas Bruun and others (eds), *The European Social Charter and the Employment Relation* (Hart 2017).

⁸⁹ O'Cinnéide, 'The Right to Work in International Human Rights Law' (n 37) 99–122.

⁹⁰ The Appendix states that persons covered by the ESC's provisions 'include foreigners only in so far as they are nationals of other Parties lawfully resident or working regularly within the territory of the Party concerned'.

⁹¹ See European Committee on Social Rights, *Conclusions 2015*, 'Statement of Interpretation: the right of refugees under the Charter', 2015_163_10/EN, 8 October 2015.

⁹² Urfan Khaliq, 'The EU and the European Social Charter: Never the Twain Shall Meet?' (2013) 15 *Cambridge Yearbook of European Legal Studies* 169.

with equivalent provisions in the ESC, with the wording of these provisions at times being very similar to their Social Charter counterparts. These include article 15, which covers the right to choose an occupation and engage in work: the wording of this article is very similar to article 1 of the ESC. Furthermore, the explanations relating to the rights contained in the EU Charter, prepared under the authority of the Praesidium of the Convention which drafted this Charter, explicitly states that the provisions of article 15 are based upon the equivalent provisions of the ESC.¹⁷⁹ By virtue of Article 52(7) of the EU Charter, these explanations should be given 'due regard' by EU and national courts in interpreting the Charter. So it is logical to infer that the interpretation given by the ESCR to the right to work as protected in article 1 and subsequent provisions of the ESC should be taken into account in interpreting EU law in general, and in particular the provisions of article 15 of the EU Charter.⁹³

ii. Systemic Integration of the Right to Work into the ECHR & the concept of 'legal vulnerability'

When interpreting civil and political rights, the ECtHR takes into account that their effectiveness depends on access to work and other core socio-economic entitlements. This has resulted in a partial integration of right to work concerns into the ECHR jurisprudence.⁹⁴ In *Niemietz v Germany*, the court stated that article 8 (the right to privacy) includes 'the right to establish and develop relationships with other human beings', including in working life as it is in that context that 'the majority of people have a significant, if not the greatest, opportunity of developing relationships with the outside world'.⁹⁵ By extension, the ECtHR has interpreted article 8 and other Convention rights, taken together with the right to non-discrimination set out in article 14, as requiring States to protect individuals against discriminatory barriers to employment. Thus, in *Sidabras v Lithuania*,⁹⁶ the ECtHR held that 'a far-reaching ban' on taking up employment' violated article 8 ECHR. Notably the court's reasoning reflected the dual value of the right to work.⁹⁷

The concept of vulnerability offers some promise to assist in interpreting the scope of human rights under the ECHR, positive duties in particular.⁹⁸ In particular in cases on asylum seekers, refugees and migrants in an irregular situation, the concept enables the Court to identify how vulnerability to human rights violations is structured by migration laws and practices, in a way that potentially enables a migrant context-sensitive

⁹³ Colm O'Cinnéide, 'The European Social Charter and EU Labour Law', in Alan Bogg, Cathryn Costello and Anne Davies (eds.), *Research Handbook on EU Labour Law* (Elgar, 2016), 191-213.

⁹⁴ See, in particular, Virginia Mantouvalou, 'The Protection of the Right to Work through the European Convention on Human Rights' (2014) 16 *Cambridge Yearbook of European Legal Studies* 313.

⁹⁵ *Niemietz v Germany*, App No 13710/88 (ECtHR, 16 December 1992) para 29.

⁹⁶ *Sidabras v Lithuania* (2004) 42 EHRR 104.

⁹⁷ Mantouvalou, 'The Protection of the Right to Work' (n 94) 329.

⁹⁸ See generally Samantha Besson, 'La vulnérabilité et la structure des droits de l'homme' in Laurence Burgogues-Larsen (ed) *La vulnérabilité saisie par les juges en Europe* (Pedone 2014) 59; Lourdes Peroni and Alexandra Timmer, 'Vulnerable Groups: The Promise of an Emerging Concept in European Human Rights Convention Law' (2013) 11 *International Journal of Constitutional Law*; Francesca Ippolito, *Understanding Vulnerability in International Human Rights Law* (Editoriale Scientifica 2020).

interpretation of the ECHR guarantees.⁹⁹ Furthermore, the concept of structural vulnerability is particularly relevant to the discussion of labour exploitation risks, and how migration laws and practices often place asylum seekers, refugees and others with limited migration statuses at risk of extreme labour exploitation. However, the concept of 'vulnerability' also brings evident downsides. Delineating between structural and personal vulnerability is crucial if the concept is not to degenerate into stereotyping. Relatedly, the concept can become so context-sensitive as to lead to casuistic approaches. This is evident arguably in the interpretation of Article 3 ECHR in Dublin cases after *MSS*, and in particular since *Tarakhel v Switzerland*.¹⁰⁰ In some later cases, the ECtHR has seemed to suggest the individuals' apparent lack of personal vulnerability mitigates against a finding of a violation of Article 3 ECHR, in particular in potential *non-refoulement* cases.¹⁰¹ Many scholars have sought to clarify the juridical concept in light of Martha Fineman's feminist account.¹⁰² Others have engaged with an account informed by labour relations and interpersonal autonomy.¹⁰³

Article 3 ECHR

Restrictions on the work rights of asylum seekers may also contribute to inhuman and degrading living conditions, as the ECtHR recognized in *MSS v Belgium and Greece*.¹⁰⁴ Notably, asylum seekers at the time in Greece could apply for a work permit (and so had a limited legal right to work), but this was acknowledged as being ineffective. In general, it would appear that, if a state imposes work restrictions on a particular class of persons such as asylum seekers or irregular migrants, then if such persons become subject to a 'real risk' of serious poverty a breach of Article 3 ECHR may be made out.¹⁰⁵ As discussed below, this approach has been applied by the UK courts in interpreting and applying Article 3 ECHR: in the case of *Adam and Limbuela*, the UK House of Lords (the highest court at that time) held that welfare restrictions violated article 3 ECHR, where the work ban combined with withdrawal of welfare support exposed asylum seekers to a risk of destitution.¹⁰⁶

⁹⁹ Moritz Baumgärtel 'Facing the challenge of migratory vulnerability in the European Court of Human Rights' (2020) *Netherlands Quarterly of Human Rights* 12.

¹⁰⁰ Cathryn Costello and Minos Mouzarakis 'Reflections on Reading *Tarakhel*: Is "How Bad is Bad Enough" Good Enough' (2014) 10 *Asiel- & Migrantenrecht* 404, available at SSRN <http://ssrn.com/abstract=2548542> accessed 11 May 2021.

¹⁰¹ For a comparison of the ECtHR on non-refoulement, with UNTBs, revealing some of the shortcomings of the former, see Basak Çali, Cathryn Costello, and Stewart Cunningham 'Hard Protection through Soft Courts? Non-refoulement before the United Nations Treaty Bodies' (2020) 21 *German Law Journal* 355.

¹⁰² Martha Fineman, 'The Vulnerable Subject: Anchoring Equality in the Human Condition' (2008) 20 *Yale Journal of Law & Feminism* 1; Martha Fineman, 'Vulnerability and Inevitable Inequality' (2017) 4 *Oslo Law Review* 133.

¹⁰³ Costello and Freedland (n 24).

¹⁰⁴ *MSS v Belgium and Greece* (n 8).

¹⁰⁵ Colm O'Cinnéide, 'A Modest Proposal: Destitution, State Responsibility and the European Convention on Human Rights' (2008) 5 *European Human Rights Law Review* 583.

¹⁰⁶ *R (Limbuela) v Secretary of State for the Home Department* [2005] UKHL 66, [2006] 1 AC 396.

Article 4 ECHR

Article 4 ECHR (protection against slavery, servitude and forced labour) is of growing importance. While the wrongs outlined in article 4 are extreme, forced labour, often emerges when migration status limits free choice of employment.¹⁰⁷ There are also well-established links between trafficking and refugeehood.¹⁰⁸ Article 4 ECHR imposes a range of positive duties on States to take action to prevent exposure to these wrongs, including an obligation to work transnationally.¹⁰⁹ By extension, article 4 ECHR also arguably requires States to take positive steps to avoid extreme labour exploitation—an obligation which may extend to reform migration status, including work bans, to reduce risks of such exploitation.¹¹⁰

Article 4(1) ECHR states ‘No one shall be held in slavery or servitude.’ Both practices are prohibited absolutely. While ‘forced labour’ is also subject to absolute prohibition, some discrete practices are permitted which would otherwise be regarded as ‘forced labour.’¹¹¹ Slavery is defined elsewhere in international law (since 1926) as being ‘the status or condition of a person over whom any or all of the powers attaching to the right of ownership are exercised.’¹¹² The ECtHR adopted this definition in *Siliadin*.¹¹³ The UN instruments on slavery also identify other ‘practices similar to slavery’, namely debt bondage, serfdom, servile marriage and child exploitation.¹¹⁴ As slavery is formally abolished, there can be no *de jure* ‘right of ownership’ of a human being. *De jure* slavery then only persists if some remnant legal practice permits actual ownership, a rare occurrence today.¹¹⁵

Article 4(2) ECHR states that ‘No one shall be required to perform forced or compulsory labour.’ The European Court of Human Rights (‘ECtHR’) interprets ‘forced or compulsory labour’ in line with the definition provided in the ILO Convention against Force Labour

¹⁰⁷ Costello (n 25).

¹⁰⁸ See further Catherine Briddick and Vladislava Stoyanova ‘Trafficking and Refugees’ in Cathryn Costello, Michelle Foster and Jane McAdam (eds), *The Oxford Handbook of International Refugee Law* (OUP 2021 forthcoming).

¹⁰⁹ *Rantsev v Cyprus and Russia* (2010) 51 EHRR 1.

¹¹⁰ Costello (n 25).

¹¹¹ Article 4 (3) ECHR.

¹¹² *Siliadin v France* (2006) 43 EHRR 16, para 122, citing League of Nations Slavery Convention (adopted 25 September 1926, entered into force 9 March 1927) 60 LoNTS 254; UNGA; ‘Protocol Amending the Slavery Convention’ (1953) 182 UNTS 51; Supplementary Convention on the Abolition of Slavery, the Slave Trade, and Institutions and Practices Similar to Slavery (adopted 7 September 1956, entered into force 30 April 1957) 226 UNTS 3 (Supplementary Convention). The Supplementary Convention is replicated in substance as the definition of enslavement included in the 1998 Statute of the International Criminal Court. Note that under the Statute of the International Criminal Court, enslavement is a crime against humanity.

¹¹³ *Siliadin v France*, (n 112) para 122.

¹¹⁴ Supplementary Convention 1956, Article 1, recognises that the ‘institutions and practices similar to slavery’, that is: debt bondage, serfdom, servile marriages, or child exploitation; may be ‘covered by the definition of slavery contained in article 1 of the Slavery Convention of 1926’.

¹¹⁵ Cf the recent contemporary finding of chattel slavery in *Hadijatou Mani Koraou v Republic of Niger* Judgment no ECW/CCJ/JUD/06/08 (ECOWAS Community Court of Justice, 27 October 2008); See, Jean Allain, ‘Hadijatou Mani Koraou v Republic of Niger’ (2009) 103 *American Journal of International Law* 311.

(No. 29). Forced or compulsory labour accordingly means ‘all work or service which is exacted from any person under the menace of any penalty and for which the said person has not offered himself voluntarily’.¹¹⁶ The definition thus comprises two main elements: that the work or service is undertaken involuntarily, and that it is exacted under the menace of penalty. The requirement of involuntariness does not mean that entering into the work relation at the outset voluntarily means that labour is not ‘forced.’ The ILO accepts that, ‘Many victims enter forced labour situations initially out of their own choice, albeit through fraud and deception, only to discover later that they are not free to withdraw their labour.’¹¹⁷ The ability to exercise the right to quit is a litmus test for ‘forced labour.’

Many of the early Strasbourg cases concern work performed under statutory obligations as part of professional training or service. The ECtHR has developed a fact-specific and context-sensitive jurisprudence, based on the ‘normal’ expectations of the sectors.¹¹⁸ Regarding work in households, in *CN v France* the ECtHR sought to distinguish between work which could reasonably be required in respect of mutual family assistance or cohabitation and prohibited ‘forced labour’.¹¹⁹ There may be good regulatory reasons for having a sharp legal notion of ‘forced labour’ in order to distinguish normal work relations from those prohibited, treated as a violation of human rights, and criminalized. Indeed, if there is to be a criminal offence of forced labour, then there are independent liberty-protective reasons for having a clearly delineated offence. However, evoking the normally unpaid labour within families to obscure whether the work was undertaken voluntarily seems to leave domestic workers particularly vulnerable. We should recall that the French courts initially dealing with *Siliadin’s* case had rejected the argument that she was held in slavery-like conditions on the basis that long hours looking after children could not be regarded as labour exploitation, as mothers did this for their own children.¹²⁰

On the facts of *CN*, the determination seems to have been questionable, in particular in finding that as the younger girl attended school and had time to do her homework, the extent of the labour she undertook was not sufficient to be regarded as forced. This seems to conflate the quantity of work for the quality of the work relations. Moreover, rather than setting a test to examine whether, on the facts, the work was undertaken voluntarily, the Court deemed it to be so, based on expectation of normal work in households. On this point, it would have been preferable to establish criteria or hallmarks of voluntariness, but not foreclose the worker’s own voice as to the nature of her predicament. The fact that she was a minor too suggests that the Court should have been wary of deeming her work to be voluntary. Perhaps the most disturbing aspect of the judgment is how her ability to complain about her predicament to a third party was treated as an indication that she was not being subjected to forced labour.

¹¹⁶ ILO, Convention Concerning Forced or Compulsory Labour 1930 (No. 29) (adopted 10 June 1930, entered into force May 1 1932) 39 UNTS 55, cited in *Siliadin v France* (n 112) para 30; *Van der Musselle v Belgium* (1984) 6 EHRR 163 para 32; *Graziani-Weiss v Austria* App no 31950/06 (ECtHR, 18 October 2011); *Stummer v Austria* (2012) 54 EHRR 11, para 118.

¹¹⁷ ILO 2009, 6.

¹¹⁸ *Van der Musselle v Belgium* (n 116) para 32; *Graziani-Weiss v Austria* (n 116); *Steindel v Germany* App no. 29878/07 (ECtHR, 14 September 2010).

¹¹⁹ *CN and V v France* App no 67724/09 (ECtHR, 11 October 2012) para 74.

¹²⁰ (n 112).

The 'menace of penalty' may take many forms. In *Siliadin v France*, the Court considered that, although the applicant, a minor, was not threatened by a formal 'penalty', she understood herself to be at risk of being reported to the authorities for her unlawful presence and arrested.¹²¹ Similarly, in *CN v France*, while taking a rather bright line approach to the notion of whether labour is voluntary, the Court opened up the notion of 'menace of penalty', accepting that the penalty need not be 'physical violence or restraint', but rather 'can also take subtler forms, of a psychological nature, such as threats to denounce victims to the police or immigration authorities when their employment status is illegal.'¹²²

The 2017 ruling in *Chowdury and Others v Greece*¹²³ entails a judicial recognition that migrants' legal vulnerability is pertinent to understanding whether their labour exploitation amounts to forced labour. The Court noted that whether labour is *forced* depends on an assessment of the employers' 'abuse of power' or 'taking advantage of the workers' vulnerable situation.' This was the litmus test, even when the work was initially entered into voluntarily. The key paragraphs are worth setting out in full:

The Court further considers that when an employer abuses his power or takes advantage of the vulnerable situation of his workers in order to exploit them, they do not offer their work voluntarily. The prior consent of the victim is not sufficient to exclude qualifying labor as forced labor. Whether a person volunteers their work is a factual question that must be considered in light of all the relevant circumstances of a case.¹²⁴

And then applying the standards for assessing forced labour to the facts, the Court found that:

In this case, the Court notes that the applicants commenced work when they found themselves *in a situation of vulnerability*, as migrants in an irregular situation without resources and at risk of being arrested, detained and deported. They undoubtedly realized that if they stopped working, they would never collect the arrears of their wages, the amount of which was constantly increasing as the days passed. Even supposing that, at the time of hiring, the applicant volunteered their work and believed in good faith that they would receive their wages, the situation subsequently changed as a result of the behaviour of their employers.¹²⁵

¹²¹ Para 118.

¹²² *CN and V v France* (n119) para 77.

¹²³ *Chowdury* (n 9); *Stoyanova* (n 9).

¹²⁴ Para 96. '96. La Cour considère, en outre, que, lorsqu'un employeur abuse de son pouvoir ou tire profit de la situation de vulnérabilité de ses ouvriers afin de les exploiter, ceux-ci n'offrent pas leur travail de plein gré. Le consentement préalable de la victime n'est pas suffisant pour exclure de qualifier un travail de travail forcé. La question de savoir si une personne offre son travail de plein gré est une question factuelle qui doit être examinée à la lumière de toutes les circonstances pertinentes d'une affaire.'

¹²⁵ Para 97. 'En l'espèce, la Cour note que les requérants ont commencé à travailler alors qu'ils se trouvaient dans une situation de vulnérabilité, en tant que migrants en situation irrégulière n'ayant pas de ressources et courant le risque d'être arrêtés, détenus et expulsés. Les intéressés se rendaient sans doute compte que, s'ils arrêtaient de travailler, ils n'allaient jamais percevoir les arriérés de leurs salaires dont le montant ne cessait d'augmenter au fil des jours. À supposer même que, au moment de leur embauche, les requérants aient offert leur travail de plein gré et

The Court in *Chowdury* found that the Greek authorities had erred in their legal assessment, effectively looking for the indicia of *servitude*.

‘Servitude’ is as an aggravated form of forced labour, where the obligation to provide one’s services is based on coercion.¹²⁶ It is a ‘particularly serious form of denial of freedom.’ Its hallmark was that ‘in addition to the obligation to perform certain services for others’ there was an ‘obligation for the "serf" to live on another person’s property and the impossibility of altering his condition.’¹²⁷ There appears to be a conflation of servitude and serfdom here, not inappropriate on the facts given that the applicant was confined to the home, but conceptually misleading. While the institution of serfdom varied greatly across territories and over time, its basic feature was that serf’s obligations to work for the landowner came by virtue of their inherited status of serf.¹²⁸ By virtue of its ascriptive status, the serf had no choice of employer and usually, little prospect of exiting that status.¹²⁹

For servitude to be established, it is sufficient if the perceived inability to alter one’s predicament is based on ‘objective elements created or maintained by those responsible.’¹³⁰ In *Siliadin*, the finding of ‘servitude’ was based on the fact that in addition to the forced labour, the applicant was a minor, lacked resources, and so was completely dependent on her employers. In *CN and V v France*, the first applicant was deemed to be the victim of servitude (and forced labour), while the second was not.¹³¹ The first applicant, the older of the two sisters, worked long hours and was socially isolated. In contrast, the younger sister attended school, and was given time to do her homework. On this basis, the unpaid chores she did were not regarded as undertaken involuntarily. The threshold of servitude was met in the first applicant’s case as in addition to forced labour, she felt that her condition was ‘was permanent and could not change, especially as it lasted four years.’¹³² In contrast, as the younger girl attended school, she was able to alert the school nurse to her situation.

Article 14 ECHR

This indirect integration of the right to work into ECHR jurisprudence is notable in the Court’s Article 14 (non-discrimination) jurisprudence, in particular as it relates to the rights of migrants. Article 14 ECHR is of increasing importance in relation to asylum

qu’ils aient cru en toute bonne foi qu’ils allaient percevoir leurs salaires, la situation a changé par la suite en raison du comportement de leurs employeurs.’ Translation authors’ own.

¹²⁶ *Siliadin v France* (n 112) para 124; *Seguin v France* (2006) 43 EHRR 16.

¹²⁷ *Siliadin v France* (n 112) para 123.

¹²⁸ This is reflected in the UN Supplementary Convention, which defines serfdom as ‘the condition or status of a tenant who is by law, custom or agreement bound to live and labour on land belonging to another person and to render some determinate service to such other person, whether for reward or not, and is not free to change his status.’

¹²⁹ The lord of the manor could manumit the serf, or in some instances the serf could buy his freedom. Some laws providing means for serfs to escape and gain freedom, for instance in England, a serf who escaped and lived in a borough for a year and a day evading capture became a burgher.

¹³⁰ *CN and V v France* (n119) para 91.

¹³¹ *CN and V v France* (n119) on forced labour, see para 77; on servitude, paras 92-93.

¹³² *CN and V v France* (n119) para 92.

seekers and refugees, in particular when they are treated differently to other migrants, or where their treated is indirect discrimination on another ground. Article 14 is an open-ended non-discrimination guarantee, applicable in conjunction with the substantive rights under the Convention. In terms of the grounds of discrimination, one may distinguish between the legal treatment of prohibited grounds such as race and sex, where there are few permissible justifications, and 'other grounds' such as migration status (which includes the status of asylum seeker, refugee, family migrant or other), where treatment will violate Article 14 only if there is no objective justification. Distinctions between different categories of asylum seekers and refugees may be indirect discrimination in which case it will be extremely likely to violate Article 14 ECHR. In with *Biao v. Denmark*, the Grand Chamber found a violation of Article 14 of the ECHR in the difference in treatment between certain categories of Danish nationals regarding family reunification, allowing only those who had been Danish nationals for 28 years to enjoy the right.¹³³ The workings of the Danish rules were found to amount to indirect discrimination on grounds of ethnicity. Since it follows from case law that, 'no difference in treatment based exclusively or to a decisive extent on a person's ethnic origin is capable of being justified in a contemporary democratic society',¹³⁴ the Court went on to examine whether this indirect discrimination could be justified by 'compelling or very weighty reasons unrelated to ethnic origin' and answered in the negative.¹³⁵ It found that the 28-year rule was based on undocumented, partly biased, general assumptions and 'rather speculative arguments' about when Danish nationals had created strong ties with Denmark and that this rule, when applied to the applicant, did not allow for his strong ties to Denmark to be taken into account.

*Hode and Abdi v UK*¹³⁶ concerned the difference in treatment between refugees' spouses who married post-flight and other migrants entitled to family reunification. The Court held that refugees with post-flight spouses were similarly situated with migrant students and workers, who were entitled to family reunification irrespective of when the marriage was contracted. The similarity was rooted in the fact that 'as students and workers, whose spouses were entitled to join them, were usually granted a limited period of leave to remain in the United Kingdom, the Court considers that they too were in an analogous position to the applicants for the purpose of Article 14 of the Convention.'¹³⁷ The UK failed to demonstrate that this difference in treatment pursued a legitimate aim sufficient for such difference to be justified. The UK had attempted to argue that it treated migrant workers and students better as it was attempting to attract them to the UK, while it was accepting refugees as a matter of international obligation, but not seeking to compete with other states to attract them.¹³⁸ While the Court held that offering incentives to certain groups of immigrants may amount to a legitimate aim for the purposes of Article 14 of the ECHR, it noted that this justification had not previously been offered by the UK

¹³³ *Biao v Denmark* App no 38590/10 (ECtHR, 24 May 2016).

¹³⁴ *ibid*, para 94.

¹³⁵ *ibid*, para 114.

¹³⁶ *Hode and Abdi v UK* App no 22341/09 (ECtHR, 6 November 2012).

¹³⁷ *ibid*, para 50.

¹³⁸ *ibid*, para 36, 'on the other hand, although the Government were committed to honouring their international obligations with respect to refugees, they had not sought to encourage refugees and asylum seekers to choose to travel to the United Kingdom by offering additional incentives.'

for this policy.¹³⁹ In *Niedzwiecki v Germany* the Court, echoing the German Federal Constitutional Court, held that it could not discern sufficient reasons justifying a difference of treatment between non-nationals as regards access to child benefits which was based on the type of residence permit.¹⁴⁰ In its reasoning, which was upheld by the Court, the German Federal Constitutional Court pointed out that insofar as the distinction was aimed at limiting the grant of child benefits to aliens who were likely to stay permanently in Germany, the criteria applied were inappropriate to reach that aim since the fact that a person held a limited residence title did not constitute a sufficient basis for predicting the duration of his or her stay in Germany.¹⁴¹

This caselaw is potentially of significance to assessing the legality of differentiated work rights restrictions.

5. The Right to Work as an EU Fundamental Right

EU law protects fundamental rights as general principles of EU law and in the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights. The Charter binds the EU institutions in all in its activities, irrespective of whether they are internal or externally-oriented.¹⁴² It binds the Member States when the 'implement EU law.' As well as containing in Article 5 a prohibition of slavery, forced labour and trafficking, the Charter contains an express right to work in Article 15, stating:

Article 15 - Freedom to choose an occupation and right to engage in work

1. Everyone has the right to engage in work and to pursue a freely chosen or accepted occupation.
2. Every citizen of the Union has the freedom to seek employment, to work, to exercise the right of establishment and to provide services in any Member State
3. Nationals of third countries who are authorised to work in the territories of the Member States are entitled to working conditions equivalent to those of citizens of the Union.

Several other rights in the Charter are work related, including Article 16 on 'Freedom to conduct a business' which provides 'The freedom to conduct a business in accordance with Union law and national laws and practices is recognised.' Title IV entitled 'Solidarity' contains several work-related rights, some of which are deemed to be for 'workers' (eg Article 27 - Workers' right to information and consultation within the undertaking); Article 28 - Right of collective bargaining and action (for workers, employers and their respective organisations), Article 30 (Article 30 - Protection in the event of unjustified dismissal); Article 31 - Fair and just working conditions. In contrast, the right of access to placement services is for 'everyone.' While some rights in Title V are 'Citizens'

¹³⁹ *ibid*, para 53, citing *A (Afghanistan) v. Secretary of State for the Home Department* [2009] EWCA Civ 825 ; *FH (Post-flight spouses) Iran* [2010] UKUT 275 (IAC).

¹⁴⁰ *Niedzwiecki v Germany* App no 58453/00 (ECtHR, 25 October 2005) , paras 27-33. Cf. also *Okpiz v Germany* App no 59140/00 (ECtHR, 25 October 2005) on the same issue and with the same result.

¹⁴¹ *ibid*.

¹⁴² Violeta Moreno-Lax and Cathryn Costello 'The Extraterritorial Application of the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights: From Territoriality to Facticity, the Effectiveness Model' in Steve Peers and others (eds), *Commentary on the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights* (Hart Publishing, 2014).

Rights' by definition most of the pertinent Charter rights apply to all persons or all workers irrespective of nationality. While Article 15(3) seems to acknowledge implicitly that there is a legitimate process of deciding which TCNs are 'authorised to work in the territories of the Member States', this provision relates only to 'working conditions.' There is no nationality or status-related limitation on the right to work.¹⁴³

As discussed in the section of this paper dealing with the European Social Charter (ESC), the provisions of many rights set out in the EU Charter drew upon or were directly based upon the provisions of the ESC. This includes Article 15 of the EU Charter. Thus, as previously argued, this right and other EU Charter provisions should be interpreted by reference to the interpretation given by the European Committee on Social Rights to the right to work as protected in the ESC.¹⁴⁴ The ECSR has consistently emphasised the central importance of the right to work to human flourishing. It has also interpreted the provisions of the ESC as requiring equal treatment between refugees and asylum seekers and nationals, except where a State party can show a compelling justification for differential treatment, and crucially that refugees should in all circumstances enjoy the protection of the essential features of the relevant ESC rights.¹⁴⁵ Thus, by logical extension, these standards should be taken into account in the interpretation of the equivalent provisions of Article 15 and associated articles of the EU Charter.

As mentioned at the outset, EU legislation currently permits Member States to limit asylum seekers right to work for their first 9 months while they await status determination. Article 15 of the RCD provides:

1. Member States shall ensure that applicants have access to the labour market no later than 9 months from the date when the application for international protection was lodged if a first instance decision by the competent authority has not been taken and the delay cannot be attributed to the applicant.
2. Member States shall decide the conditions for granting access to the labour market for the applicant, in accordance with their national law, while ensuring that applicants have effective access to the labour market.

For reasons of labour market policies, Member States may give priority to Union citizens and nationals of States parties to the Agreement on the European Economic Area, and to legally resident third-country nationals.

3. Access to the labour market shall not be withdrawn during appeals procedures, where an appeal against a negative decision in a regular procedure has suspensive effect, until such time as a negative decision on the appeal is notified.

As mentioned at the outset, EU Member States adopt varying approaches in implementation of this provision.¹⁴⁶ In some instances, the right to work is tightly restricted sectorally, in a manner that may infringe Article 2(2) in that while Member States may impose conditions, these must nonetheless ensure 'effective access to the

¹⁴³ See further Diamond Ashiagbor, 'Article 15 – Freedom to Choose an Occupation and Right to Engage in Work' in Steve Peers and others (eds), *Commentary on the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights* (Hart Publishing, 2014).

¹⁴⁴ Colm O'Cinnéide, 'The European Social Charter and EU Labour Law' (n 93) 191-213.

¹⁴⁵ See European Committee on Social Rights, *Conclusions 2015*, (n 91).

¹⁴⁶ See EMN (n 20).

labour market.’ In particular, the Article must be interpreted in a manner compatible with the EU Charter (and in turn its sources in international human rights law), so any limitations on the right to work must be strictly construed. Some Member States link the right to work with the apparent strength of the asylum claim, requiring some applicants to reside for prolonged periods in designated residences without work rights. These practices may be indirect discrimination on other grounds, or be deemed to be unjustifiable restrictions of the substantive right to work.

The full implications of Article 15 of the Charter remain to be seen. In Advocate General Jean Richard de la Tour’s Opinion of 3 September 2020 in *KS & MHK* noted the dual value of the right to work, stating that ‘The right to work, as enshrined in numerous international and regional human rights instruments, plays a role not only in the personal development of the individual and in his or her social and economic integration into society, but also in preserving his or her dignity.’¹⁴⁷ The Opinion also cited the ICESCR General Comment No 18, and the ruling of the Supreme Court of Ireland (discussed below) which held that a protracted ban on asylum seekers’ working was a violation of the right to work.¹⁴⁸ In assessing the value of the right to work, the AG noted in particular that:

For an applicant, work therefore clearly contributes to the preservation of his or her dignity, since the income from that employment enables him or her not only to provide for his or her own needs, but also to obtain housing outside the reception facilities in which he or she can, where necessary, accommodate his or her family. There is no doubt that, in the context of the forced nature of migration and the often traumatic experiences associated with it, the refusal of an applicant to engage in any professional activity may increase his or her vulnerability, the precariousness of his or her situation and, sometimes, the isolation and social exclusion to which he or she is already subject, especially as the waiting period may be several months.¹⁴⁹

The Opinion also cited the CJEU ruling in *CIMADE and GISTI* (on reception conditions for Dublin transferees) noting the fact that many individuals subject to such proceedings are not in fact transferred to other Member States.

As well as noting several other practical and prudential benefits to ensuring the right to work, the Opinion also noted that ‘in a situation where there is a systemic deficiency in the reception conditions, excluding applicants from access to the regular labour market could expose the Member State to the risk of infringing the principles enshrined in Articles 1 and 4 of the Charter,’ that is the right to dignity, and protection from inhuman and degrading conditions. Of note is the AG’s citation of *ALK v Greece*,¹⁵⁰ a case applying the ruling in *MSS*, but highlighting the links between the ineffective access to the labour market, as well as other deficiencies in the reception conditions in Greece.

KS and MHK (n 11), Opinion of AG de la Tour, para 83.

¹⁴⁸ *Ibid*, para 84.

¹⁴⁹ *Ibid*, para 85.

¹⁵⁰ *ALK v Greece* Application no 63542/11 (ECtHR, 11 December 2014).

The CJEU rules in January 2021 in *KS and MHK*¹⁵¹ concerned the applicability of the right to work under Article 15 of the RCD¹⁵² to asylum seekers subject to Dublin proceedings. The Court, drawing on its previous caselaw, reiterated that the RCD applies to this subset of asylum seekers. Moreover, it affirmed the Opinion of the Advocate General referring to the importance of work for a ‘dignified standard of living’, and that ‘human dignity applies’ to asylum seekers subject to Dublin proceedings.¹⁵³ Moreover, the Court reiterated the AG’s finding on the link between work and dignity, stating that ‘work clearly contributes to the preservation of the applicant’s dignity, since the income from employment enables him or her not only to provide for his or her own needs, but also to obtain housing outside the reception facilities in which he or she can, where necessary, accommodate his or her family.’¹⁵⁴

6. Contesting Work Rights Restrictions

Many restrictions on the right to work of asylum seekers and refugees are incompatible not only with the right to work, but also with other human rights standards. This section explores two modes of realizing these rights. The first mode is domestic litigation and the second relates to transnational political processes, including under the Global Compact. The latter could be conceived of as an effort to secure the right to work ‘through international assistance and cooperation’ as required under ICESCR,¹⁵⁵ although this linkage is often not made explicit.

(a) Litigating the Right to Work

The explicit protection of the right to work in constitutional systems varies considerably,¹⁵⁶ as does these systems’ openness to international law.¹⁵⁷ This brief section examines litigation in South Africa, Hong Kong, the UK and Ireland.

Under South Africa’s original refugee legislation, refugees had the right to work but the legislation was silent on asylum seekers.¹⁵⁸ In practice, asylum seekers were left in rightless limbo during long asylum proceedings that generally led to rejection of their claims. But asylum seekers successfully challenged their economic exclusion. On work and self-employment, the South African Constitutional Court found that the restrictions in

¹⁵¹ *KS and MHK* (n 11)

¹⁵² Reception Conditions Directive (n 19).

¹⁵³ *KS and MHK* (n 11) para 69, citing Case C-179/11 *Cimade and GISTI* EU:C:2012:594 [2012] para 43.

¹⁵⁴ *Ibid.*

¹⁵⁵ ICESCR, art 2(1).

¹⁵⁶ Courtney Jung, Ran Hirschl, and Evan Rosevear. ‘Economic and Social Rights in National Constitutions’ (2014) 62 *American Journal of Comparative Law* 1043; Luke Mason, ‘Labour Rights’, *Max Planck Encyclopedia of Comparative Constitutional Law* (December 2017) <<https://oxcon.ouplaw.com/view/10.1093/law-mpeccol/law-mpeccol-e136>> accessed 11 May 2021.

¹⁵⁷ Pierre-Hugues Verdier and Mila Versteeg, ‘International Law in National Legal Systems: An Empirical Perspective’ (2015) 109 *American Journal of International Law* 514.

¹⁵⁸ Refugees Act No 130 of 1998.

question violated human dignity.¹⁵⁹ However, this caselaw did not engage deeply with international human rights or refugee law, in spite of the South African Constitution's openness thereto.¹⁶⁰ Instead, the court emphasized the combined effect the denial of the right to work and lack of State social support,¹⁶¹ emphasizing avoiding destitution, rather than the right to work *per se*.¹⁶² In spite of the constitutional protections, in 2020, new legislation entered into force¹⁶³ that is in clear tension with this constitutional jurisprudence. The new policy is to require asylum seekers to live in processing centres near land borders. Further constitutional litigation is inevitable. The existing caselaw's weakness is that its focus on non-destitution may leave open the possibility to justify work rights restrictions provided welfare provision is ensured, which would be incompatible with international human rights law. Nonetheless, we share the conclusion of Khan and Rayner that 'It is unlikely that the amendment will withstand the Supreme Court of Appeal case of *Minister of Home Affairs v Watchenuka* (2004) where it was stated that the limitation on the right to work is about more than limiting self-fulfilment, it constitutes a 'restriction upon his or her ability to live without positive humiliation and degradation and thus a violation on right to dignity.'¹⁶⁴

In *Hong Kong* the courts have developed some protections against *refoulement*.¹⁶⁵ In addition, a work ban was successfully challenged, albeit on limited grounds, in *GA v Director of Immigration*.¹⁶⁶ Given the constitutional limitations in that jurisdiction, the Court reviewed the ban on 'reasonableness' grounds, an approach that incorporated some human rights considerations. On the facts, the refusal of the permission to work was deemed unreasonable, but only in those extreme cases where a work ban may lead to inhuman and degrading conditions, rather than the right to work *per se*.¹⁶⁷

A somewhat similar approach has been taken in the *UK*, where the ECHR serves as the effective domestic bill of rights, since its incorporation by the Human Rights Act.¹⁶⁸ The UK's highest court in *Adam and Limbuela* held that welfare restrictions violated article 3 ECHR, where the work ban combined with withdrawal of welfare support exposed asylum

¹⁵⁹ s 10 of the Bill of Rights: 'Everyone has inherent dignity and the right to have their dignity respected and protected'. *Minister of Home Affairs v Watchenuka* 2004 (4) SA 326 (SCA) (right to work); *Somali Association of South Africa v Limpopo Department of Economic Development, Environment and Tourism* (48/2014) ZASCA 143 (26 September 2014) (self-employment). Cf *Union of Refugee Women and Others v Director, Private Sector Industry Regulatory Authority and Others* [2006] ZACC 23, 2007 (4) SA 395 (CC). Note powerful dissents by Mokgoro and O'Regan JJ.

¹⁶⁰ The Constitution provides that 'courts *must* consider international law in interpretation of the Bill of Rights'. See Ruvi Ziegler, 'Access to Effective Refugee Protection in South Africa: Legislative Commitment, Policy Realities, Judicial Rectifications' (2020) 10 *Constitutional Court Review* 65.

¹⁶¹ *Minister of Home Affairs v Watchenuka* (n 159) para 32.

¹⁶² *Somali Association of South Africa v Limpopo Department* (n 159) para 44.

¹⁶³ Refugees Amendment Act 11 of 2017 (RAA 2017) (1 January 2020).

¹⁶⁴ Khan and Rayner (n 12) 15.

¹⁶⁵ *GA. v. Director of Immigration*, No. 7 of 2013 (CIVIL), Hong Kong: Court of Final Appeal, 18 February 2014, available at <https://www.refworld.org/cases,HK_CFA,536cb5744.html> accessed 11 May 2021.

¹⁶⁶ *Ibid.*

¹⁶⁷ Michael Ramsden and Luke Marsh, 'The "Right to Work" of Refugees in Hong Kong: *MA v Director of Immigration*' (2013) 25 *International Journal of Refugee Law* 574.

¹⁶⁸ Human Rights Act 1998.

seekers to a risk of destitution.¹⁶⁹ Later, the English High Court in *Tekle* accepted that the right to work fell within article 8 ECHR, but higher court rulings decided that issue on other grounds.¹⁷⁰ The UK still has one of the strictest approaches in Europe to the right to work for asylum seekers, only permitting them to work after 12 months, and then only in very limited fields. These restrictions are now the focus of a broad-based campaign for legal change.¹⁷¹

The outlier in our selection is *Ireland* in terms of giving effect to the right to work *per se*. In 2017, after many years of unsuccessful political campaigns against the asylum system's restrictive features, the Supreme Court held that the ban on asylum seekers' working was a violation of the constitutional right to work.¹⁷² Notably, Ireland had not opted into the pertinent EU rules, so the ban persisted for the entire duration of the asylum process.¹⁷³ The court held that the right to work also applied to non-citizens, given its roots in human dignity, although some limitations their work rights were permissible. Although Ireland is a strictly dualist system, the court cited the ICESCR.¹⁷⁴ The implementation of the ruling has led to some labour market access for asylum seekers after nine months, although many other restrictive features of its asylum system remain.¹⁷⁵

These examples illustrate that in diverse constitutional orders, courts have tended to focus on a minimum protection against destitution, rather than protecting the right to work *per se*. The rulings also reflect the ambiguous position of asylum seekers and refugees in these diverse constitutional orders. Further research is needed on this topic of the comparative constitutional protection of refugee rights, and its links with the realization of international rights, as this brief comparison exemplifies.

(b) Leveraging the Right to Work

One of the strongest elements of the Refugee Compact is to support refugee 'self-reliance'. This concept is by no means entirely new. Refugee livelihoods have been the focus of the global refugee regime for decades if not centuries. However, the current approach appears to be a new inflection, with a fairly limited notion of self-reliance focusing on refugees as economic actors who will avoid placing a strain on the resources

¹⁶⁹ *R (Limbuella) v Secretary of State for the Home Department* (n 106).

¹⁷⁰ *R (on the application of Tekle) v Secretary of State for the Home Department* [2008] EWHC 3064. Cf *R(Rostami) v Secretary of State for the Home Department* [2013] EWHC 1494 (Admin) citing *Negassi and Lutalo* (CA) [2013] EWCA Civ 151. On appeal, both the Court of Appeal and the Supreme Court decided the case on EU law grounds exclusively. *R (on the application of ZO (Somalia) and others) (Respondents) v Secretary of State for the Home Department* [2010] UKSC 36.

¹⁷¹ Lift the Ban, 'Why People Seeking Asylum Should Have the Right to Work' (October 2018) <<https://www.refugee-action.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/2018/10/Lift-the-Ban-report.pdf>> accessed 11 May 2021; Melanie Gower, 'Asylum seekers: the permission to work policy' (21 January 2021) <<https://commonslibrary.parliament.uk/research-briefings/sn01908/>> accessed 11 May 2021.

¹⁷² *NVH v Minister for Justice & Equality and ors* [2017] IESC 35.

¹⁷³ Reception Conditions Directive (n 19).

¹⁷⁴ *NVH v Minister for Justice & Equality and ors* (n 172) para 17.

¹⁷⁵ Liam Thornton, 'Clashing Interpretations of EU Rights in Domestic Courts' (2020) 26 *European Public Law* 243.

of host countries.¹⁷⁶ Against this backdrop, and in parallel to the emergence of the Compact, a number of initiatives have been taken that aim to increase refugees' access to work. This section briefly examines three of the most prominent 'arrangements', namely those with Turkey and Jordan, noting that the Ethiopian Compact is in its incipient stage.¹⁷⁷ While the GCR has led to some action on refugees' access to work in the Global North,¹⁷⁸ most of the focus has been on host States in the Global South, and so these country focused processes are important to understanding the limits and potential of the GCR.

These processes to leverage better refugee rights in major host countries are often part of wider externalisation processes, whereby states and actors such as the EU in the Global North pay for the hosting of refugees in the Global South, whilst also enacting a range of policies to ensure that those refugees are prevented from moving onward legally in order to seek protection in the Global North. This process of refugee containment, and the process of global policy diffusion underpinning it, as the defining feature of the global refugee regime is well-established.¹⁷⁹ One feature of the containment of the past was its tendency to induce protracted refugee situations, often with refugees maintained in dependency on humanitarian assistance. While the Refugee Compact and the bilateral Compacts that preceded it share many features with the 'old' containment, a new development is the focus on self-reliance and the right to work, and the inclusion of 'development actors' to support both host communities and refugees and support inclusive development. Whether these changes go beyond mere rhetoric remains to be seen.

In general, the arrangements concerned are assumed to be non-binding, although this does not mean that they will not have legal effects.¹⁸⁰ Indeed, whether a given 'deal' or 'arrangement' is a treaty in international law cannot be stipulated in advance, and does not depend on the title used. In general, the parties treat these arrangements as non-binding, but the criteria for treaty in international law are objective. Whether, for example, the EU-Turkey statement is an international treaty is a matter of debate amongst legal scholars.¹⁸¹

¹⁷⁶ See generally Claudena Skran and Evan Easton-Calabria, 'Old Concepts Making New History: Refugee Self-reliance, Livelihoods and the "Refugee Entrepreneur"' (2020) 33 *Journal of Refugee Studies* 1.

¹⁷⁷ Gordon (n 13) 2.

¹⁷⁸ Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) and UNHCR, 'Engaging with Employers in the Hiring of Refugees: A 10-Point Multi-Stakeholder Action Plan for Employers, Refugees, Governments and Civil Society' (2018) <<https://www.oecd.org/els/mig/UNHCR-OECD-Engaging-with-employers-in-the-hiring-of-refugees.pdf>> accessed 11 May 2021.

¹⁷⁹ See Cathryn Costello 'Overcoming Refugee Containment and Crisis' (2020) 21 *German Law Journal* 17.

¹⁸⁰ On the GCM, see generally Thomas Gammeltoft-Hansen and others, *What is a Compact? Migrants' Rights and State Responsibilities regarding the design of the UN Global Compact for Safe, Orderly and Regular Migration* (Raoul Wallenberg Working Paper), <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/cmsdata/134429/What_is_Compact.pdf> accessed 11 May 2021.

¹⁸¹ See, for example, Maarten den Heijer & Thomas Spijkerboer, 'Is the EU-Turkey refugee and migration deal a treaty?' <<http://eulawanalysis.blogspot.com/2016/04/is-eu-turkey-refugee-and-migration-deal.html>> accessed 11 May 2021.

This section draws on the early assessment of these processes.

i. Turkey

One example of an arrangement that aims to improve refugees' rights, whilst also containing them away from donors' own territories and labour markets, is the March 2016 'EU-Turkey Statement'.¹⁸² Syrian refugees' with 'temporary protection' status in Turkey did not initially enjoy the right to work. The Statement notes the 'progress already achieved' 'including Turkey's opening of its labour market to Syrians under temporary protection'¹⁸³ referring to Turkey decision in January 2016 to grant the right to work. In spite of this 'progress' the right to work remains heavily restricted in practice, with work permits being costly and held by the employer. It appears that less than one per cent of Syrians in Turkey are employed under these permits,¹⁸⁴ with the gender breakdown 10:1 men to women.¹⁸⁵ The situation of refugees of other nationalities is even more precarious in Turkey, with requirements to reside in 'satellite cities'. Those in need of work generally evade these restrictions and work informally in major cities.¹⁸⁶

ii. Jordan

Under the 2016 Jordan Compact, Jordan agreed with 'donor states' to grant up to 200,000 Syrians work permits in exchange for World Bank loans and improved market access to the EU for goods manufactured in designated Special Economic Zones (SEZs), provided at least 15% of the workers were Syrian.¹⁸⁷ As Lenner and Turner have explained, the SEZ element in particular failed to deliver, as refugees were neither willing nor able to work under the poor conditions in the relevant sector, where most workers are migrant women from Southeast Asia.¹⁸⁸ These women's tied migrant status means they often live in dormitories, work long hours, and invariably leave their children, if they have any, in their home countries. Aside from the failed SEZ plan, the Compact has been impactful. Official data indicates over 150, 000 permits issued.¹⁸⁹ In terms of its deeper impact, it remains unclear whether the work permit improves pay or working conditions.¹⁹⁰ One striking further finding in relation to the Jordan Compact is that 'access to self-employment (...)' has become even more restrictive for refugees since the Compact, which, given the

¹⁸² European Council, 'EU-Turkey Statement' (Press Release 144/16, 18 March 2016) para 1 <<https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2016/03/18/eu-turkey-statement/>> accessed 11 May 2021.

¹⁸³ Ibid.

¹⁸⁴ Statistics from 2018 indicate that 27,830 permits were issued, while the Syrian refugee population is estimated to be 3.5 million. AIDA Asylum Information Database, 'Turkey: Access to the Labour Market' <<https://www.asylumineurope.org/reports/country/turkey/access-labour-market-0>> accessed 30 June 2020.

¹⁸⁵ Ibid. 25, 457 permits to men, 2,473 to women.

¹⁸⁶ Clemens, Huang, and Graham (n 47) 42.

¹⁸⁷ By means of loosening EU 'rules of origin'. See Decision No 1/2016 of the EU-Jordan Association Committee of 19 July 2016 [2016] OJ L233/6.

¹⁸⁸ Katharina Lenner and Lewis Turner, 'Making Refugees Work? The Politics of Integrating Syrian Refugees into the Labor Market in Jordan' (2019) 28 Middle East Critique 65.

¹⁸⁹ 179,445 permits from 1 Jan 2016– 31 Jan 2020. Ministry of Labour Syrian Refugee Unit, 'Syrian Refugee Unit Work Permit Progress Report' (January 2020) <<https://data2.unhcr.org/en/documents/download/73881>> accessed 11 May 2021.

¹⁹⁰ Gordon (n 13) 3.

preference of women for home-based work, has a detrimental gender impact'.¹⁹¹ Overall, the Jordan Compact has met with criticism, in particular from the perspective of ensuring decent work,¹⁹² although when compared to Turkey, clearly some access to the formal labour market has been assured. Although it has been suggested that Jordan is a 'good practice' example as regards the GCR, the range of pledges made by diverse actors under the GCR¹⁹³ contrasts with the core focus on work of the Jordan Compact. While it is too early to assess the impact of the GCR pledges, it appears as yet that their impact is limited.

iii. Ethiopia

The Ethiopian Compact has led to a shift in the right to work of refugees, albeit as yet only on paper. Initially, the Compact also focused on export-oriented industrial parks, but lessons were learned from the Jordan Compact's failures. At the end of 2019, its sectors and geographic areas remain to be determined. However, even aside from questions of implementation, the Compact rests on weak normative commitments. In particular, the 'Refugees Proclamation' ties refugee work rights to those granted to other non-citizens in Ethiopia, which are restrictive.¹⁹⁴

iv. Assessment

Securing the right to decent work for refugees, in particular in developing countries, is challenging. These processes are assumed to be political 'deals' rather than binding treaties (although that is a matter for assessment). The 'parties' are host States and donors, with refugees absent from the table. Aside from the failure to engage with those most affected, without some clear benchmarking and monitoring, can easily become empty promises, or even lead to a deterioration in refugee rights. It has been suggested that getting national governments on board is only part of the process, and that local engagement is crucial.¹⁹⁵

Secondly, at present, these 'deals' often promise permits for refugees' *employers*, rather than for refugees themselves. Issuing permits to employers may limit free choice of employment, a vital element of the right to work. While many labour migration systems issue work permits to the employer rather than the worker, this practice is invariably a risk factor for exploitation. A recent study confirmed that refugees were perceiving a number of risks' to their proposed mode of labour market inclusion, including greater exploitation risks as 'the power remained with employers' and 'a work permit (which was time-bound and conditional) was not the same as having the right to work'.¹⁹⁶

¹⁹¹ Amanda Gray Meral, 'Assessing the Jordan Compact One Year On: An Opportunity or a Barrier to Better Achieving Refugees' Right to Work' (2020) 33 *Journal of Refugee Studies* 42, 56.

¹⁹² Ala Al-Mahaidi, 'Securing Economic Livelihoods for Syrian Refugees: The Case for a Human Rights-Based Approach to the Jordan Compact' (2020) 25 *The International Journal of Human Rights* 203.

¹⁹³ Tsourapas and Verduijn note that 'Currently, 48 pledges have been made for GCR implementation in Jordan by NGOs, international organisations, states, academic organizations, faith-based organisations, refugee groups, sports organisations, and the private sector.' (n 14) 16.

¹⁹⁴ Gordon (n 13) 26.

¹⁹⁵ Alexander Betts, *The Wealth of Refugees: How Displaced People Can Build Economies* (OUP 2021).

¹⁹⁶ Caitlin Wake and Veronique Barbelet, 'Towards a Refugee Livelihoods Approach: Findings from Cameroon, Jordan, Malaysia and Turkey' (2020) 33 *Journal of Refugee Studies* 125, 137 (on refugees in Turkey and Jordan).

A third set of concerns arises around the links between these processes and mobility restrictions. The Jordan Compact was initially framed around a 'zonal development model' which envisaged refugees working in SEZs and living in adjacent camps. The Ethiopian Compact initially also focused on SEZs. Other new models of 'self-reliance' piloted as part of the GCR implementation also focus on particular settlements.¹⁹⁷ Given that mobility restrictions generally hamper the realization of the right to work,¹⁹⁸ that these processes seem to normalize mobility restrictions, which are in themselves often a human rights violation, is itself of concern.

Concerning non-discrimination, serious issues around nationality, race, and gender discrimination arise. Many of the deals only leverage better rights for one particular groups of refugees, ignoring the others, as both the EU-Turkey deal and Jordan Compact exemplify. Both Turkey and Jordan host many different refugee nationalities, and Jordan is a significant host of Palestine refugees. Underlying this explicit nationality discrimination may be race or ethnicity discrimination by proxy.¹⁹⁹ The processes outlined above also illustrate a stunning failure to consider women's rights, in particular the deeply gendered nature of work and care.

The processes discussed above reflect many of the structural global inequalities that underpin refugee containment. A further challenge emerges from the range of actors involved in these processes. Beyond these specific agreements discussed above, the World Bank now offers financing to support refugee inclusion.²⁰⁰ The ILO has recently remerged into the refugee rights field.²⁰¹ The contrasting roles of the ILO and international economic institutions in the refugee regime are in need of greater scholarly attention.²⁰² Refugees have not been included in the decision-making, and as Gordon concludes, '[d]ecent work for refugees will not be achieved as an add-on; it must be part of the plan from the beginning'.²⁰³

¹⁹⁷ Alexander Betts and others, *The Kalobeyei Model: Towards Self-Reliance for Refugees?* (Refugee Studies Centre 2019).

¹⁹⁸ Clemens, Huang, and Graham (n 47).

¹⁹⁹ See further Tendayi Achiume 'Race, Refugees, and International Law' in Cathryn Costello, Michelle Foster and Jane McAdam (eds), *The Oxford Handbook of International Refugee Law* (OUP 2021 *forthcoming*) on race discrimination by proxy.

²⁰⁰ Global Concessional Financing Facility, 'Supported Projects' <<https://globalcff.org/supported-projects/>> accessed 11 May 2021; International Development Association World Bank Group, 'IDA18 Regional Sub-Window for Refugees and Host Communities' <<http://ida.worldbank.org/replenishments/ida-18replenishments/ida18-regional-sub-window-for-refugees-host-communities>> accessed 11 May 2021.

²⁰¹ ILO, 'Guiding Principles on the Access of Refugees and Other Forcibly Displaced Persons to the Labour Market' (28 November 2016) < https://www.ilo.org/global/topics/labour-migration/publications/WCMS_536440/lang--en/index.htm> accessed 11 May 2021; ILO, 'Recommendation R205: Employment and Decent Work for Peace and Resilience' (16 June 2017).

²⁰² Sarah Deardoff Miller, 'The GCR and the Role of Development Actors with Refugees: A Game-Changer, or More of the Same?' (2019) 57(6) *International Migration* 173; Leah Zamore, 'Refugees, Development, Debt, Austerity: A Selected History' (2018) 6 *Journal on Migration and Human Security* 26.

²⁰³ Gordon (n 13) 4.

7. Conclusion

This paper demonstrates that the right to decent work in international human rights law, in particular its 'minimum core', applies to asylum seekers and refugees. Many contemporary restrictions on asylum seekers and refugees' access to work are arguably in breach of ICESCR and regional human rights treaties. Article 15 of the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights guarantees a right to work of universal scope, opening up to potential challenge restrictions of work right of asylum seekers and refugees. Making the right to decent work effective is thus the key challenge, and as demonstrated, both domestic and regional litigation and transnational leveraging often lose sight of the basic elements of decent work, focusing on minimal elements of anti-destitution, or forgetting the basic insight that decent work is not about empowering employers, but should empower refugees *qua* workers and employers.

The paper has identified many issues in need of greater scholarly attention throughout, in particular in relation to the 'informal' economy, gendered and racialized divisions of labour, and the role of law in both limiting work rights, as well as enabling decent work. The GCR and the Compacts suggest an unmooring of refugee protection from law and normative commitments. However, for these processes to be meaningful and effective, establishing participatory forms of monitoring and benchmarking is vital, as are clear commitments rooted in human rights. The EU is a crucial actor in this regard, not only as its Member States host many asylum seekers and refugees. Its asylum policies are widely emulated, and so have a global impact. Moreover, it plays a key role in global processes that seek to leverage better protection for refugees in the main host states outside the EU. If these processes are to improve refugees' lives, a human rights-based approach to the right to work is vital.

Appendix 1

Article 27 CRPD

Article 27 – Work and employment

1. States Parties recognize the right of persons with disabilities to work, on an equal basis with others; this includes the right to the opportunity to gain a living by work freely chosen or accepted in a labour market and work environment that is open, inclusive and accessible to persons with disabilities.

States Parties shall safeguard and promote the realization of the right to work, including for those who acquire a disability during the course of employment, by taking appropriate steps, including through legislation, to, inter alia:

a) Prohibit discrimination on the basis of disability with regard to all matters concerning all forms of employment, including conditions of recruitment, hiring and employment, continuance of employment, career advancement and safe and healthy working conditions;

b) Protect the rights of persons with disabilities, on an equal basis with others, to just and favourable conditions of work, including equal opportunities and equal remuneration for work of equal value, safe and healthy working conditions, including protection from harassment, and the redress of grievances;

c) Ensure that persons with disabilities are able to exercise their labour and trade union rights on an equal basis with others;

d) Enable persons with disabilities to have effective access to general technical and vocational guidance programmes, placement services and vocational and continuing training;

e) Promote employment opportunities and career advancement for persons with disabilities in the labour market, as well as assistance in finding, obtaining, maintaining and returning to employment;

f) Promote opportunities for self-employment, entrepreneurship, the development of cooperatives and starting one's own business;

g) Employ persons with disabilities in the public sector;

h) Promote the employment of persons with disabilities in the private sector through appropriate policies and measures, which may include affirmative action programmes, incentives and other measures;

i) Ensure that reasonable accommodation is provided to persons with disabilities in the workplace;

j) Promote the acquisition by persons with disabilities of work experience in the open labour market;

k) Promote vocational and professional rehabilitation, job retention and return-to-work programmes for persons with disabilities.

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2. States Parties shall ensure that persons with disabilities are not held in slavery or in servitude, and are protected, on an equal basis with others, from forced or compulsory labour.

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